

LOWER BACK PAIN: WHAT ARE THE TREATMENT OPTIONS.

Back pain in general is a pain in the back that is usually produced by heavy lifting, twisting, and improper posture. Low back pain is the most frequent ailment when one ages, or when one is motionless and has been driving for long hours. Since low back pain is never a cause of life-threatening conditions, it is still thought of as a health problem for most people. However, in today's age, there has been a decrease in back injuries in the workplace because of the increased awareness of this problem. If you have a back injury visit [Back Center](#).

There are various precautionary measures and there are improved treatments for low back pain, ranging from self-care at home, medications, and medical management. Visit **Back Center Nj** to know your option.

Utilizing simple but significant changes to your lifestyle and presenting yourself for treatment at [Back Center New Jersey](#) can bring about major improvements in your low back pain.

1) Self-Care at Home - an initial lower back pain treatment.

Sleeping:

- People with low back pain are recommended to sleep with a pillow between the knees while lying on one side.

- They can likewise lie level on the bed with cushions under their knees.
- This improves support to your back and stops further injury.
- Don't take bed rest for more than 2 days as it can worsen your condition.

Low back pain exercises:

- These comprise Pelvic tilt, Back twist, Hamstring stretch, knee to chest, shoulder shrug, etc. are also helpful to stimulate muscles and favors movement and joint flexibility; it also helps relieve pain.
- Walking is also considered a part of exercise that should be performed gently and carefully.
- Exercise can prove a great help to people returning to their normal activities.

Over counter drugs (Nonprescription drugs):

Anti-Pain Ibuprofen (Advil, Motrin):

This is indicated for the short treatment of low back pain. There can be an increased risk of gastric ulcer or gastric bleeding when used for a long time. This is usually taken after a meal. It's better to consult your doctor when you are to take these.

Hot/cold therapy:

- You can use it as a matter of choice and should not exceed for more than 15 minutes.

- Hot therapy with the placing of a heating pad can help in reducing swelling if there's any.
- Cold therapy with the usage of an ice pack can help lower back pain as the cold has an anesthetic effect.

Avoid longevity bed rest

- This extends the recovery period of the back, as it can likely develop depression.
- Bed rest weakens muscle tone.

2) Medical Treatment - if the pain is chronic, it is best to discuss with your doctor for adequate treatment.

Prescription drugs:

- Nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory medications (NSAIDs) - These drugs are the foundation of medical treatment for the relief of back pain.
- COX-2 inhibitors (Celecoxib). As these are a powerful pain reliever, it is additionally broadly utilized as it avoids gastrointestinal dying..
- Steroids - Oral. These can be best benefited by those who have acute low back pain.
- Injectables.

This can have an extended relief of pain since the immersion is faster than oral. However, it should be given with discretion and should be done by a professional.